
THE PRINCIPLES OF MAINTAINING THE STRUCTURE OF THE FAMILY SYSTEM IN THE 21ST CENTURY IN THE LIGHT OF ISLAMIC TEACHINGS

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ABSTRACT

The meaning of family harmony is that the marital relationship of man and woman is stable. As such, every member of it, be it an agricultural or an industrial society, is bound by its decisions. And the basis of social stability is family harmony. In a society in which there is no restriction on the relationship between men and women, children are not an integral part of the family and elders are not respected, the society is prone to sexual immorality and criminal negligence, devoid of compassion and mercy and devoid of human compassion. goes Family disorder is also the cause of the current social chaos, irresponsibility in sexual relations, frequent divorces, restraint of reproduction and lack of respect for the elderly are the evils that have destroyed stability and peace. In this article, the thesis writer will close his pen "in the light of the principles of Islamic teachings on maintaining the structure of the family system in the 21st century.

Keyword: Quran, Hadith, books, books of Allama Iqbal

Introduction:

The word family is a Persian language word, the Urdu meaning of family is gharana, tribe, some people of a family. The origin of the family the family relationship comes into existence from the relationship between man and woman, based on this basic marital relationship, the family system of human life moves forward. Then children are born from the relationship of husband and wife and their children take the form of man and woman and come as a form of tribe and family. And then this unity spreads and becomes a society. In the same way, the links of human life are formed. Because the simple and initial form of the family is a stable relationship between a man and a woman in the bond of marriage, and in the extensive training there are all the elements that are related to men and women in one way or another. The explanation is something like this: that the word family is an English language word which is derived from the Latin language, which means a group, which includes parents, children, servants, etc. In his book "Marriage and Family", F. Namakvapani defines family in these words: A relationship consisting of husband, wife and children which is relatively common. According to Sims and Keller, a family is a short social organization that includes at least two generations and is distinguished by being

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connected by the same blood relationship through marriage. Therefore, men and women have the basic status of living the social system of the family.¹ Now, in the next line, we will look at the family system in the light of the Qur'an and Hadith so that it becomes clear that whether it is the 21st century or all the families that will come until the Day of Judgment, the survival of all of them is based on the blessed life of Khatam-ul-Nabi(peace be upon him.)

Allah says:

وَلَقَدْ أَرْسَلْنَا رُسُلًا مِّن قَبْلِكَ وَجَعَلْنَا لَهُم أَزْوَاجًا وَذُرِّيَّةً^٢

"Indeed, we sent many messengers before him, and for all these messengers we (Allah) made wives and children."

From this blessed verse of Allah, it is clear that the family members It is in a relationship, then the relationship and the generation and then the family will continue to be formed. That is, including our last prophet Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa (peace be upon him), the Lord Almighty sent more or less one hundred and twenty-four thousand messengers and prophets on this earth. All of them who settled in the world were human beings, and all these prophets and messengers had their own family system and they also had different tribes and they all had wives and children. They were from the human race, because if they were angels, then it would be impossible for us humans to get to know them and be close to them, which would have destroyed the original purpose of God sending the prophets and messengers. If the angels came to the world, there would be neither their family, nor their tribe, nor theirs They had wives and children, from which it was known that all the prophets were human beings of the same sex, they were not angels or any light creatures in human form. There will be at least three.³

Similarly, at another place in the Holy Quran it is said:

ومن آياته ان خلق لكم من انفسكم ازواجاً لتسكنوا اليها وجعل بينكم مودة ورحمة ان
في ذلك لآيات لقوم يتفكرون^٤

"And one of the signs of Allah is that Allah created for you women of the human race, so that when a man among you goes to his women, you may feel comfort and Allah created love and affection between husband and wife, indeed there are signs in that for those who pay attention."

That is, Allah Almighty created women from your own gender so that those women can become your wives after marriage. Because every scholar knows that Allah Almighty sent the first woman Hazrat Hawa (peace be upon her) and Hazrat Adam (peace

be upon him) on this earth. Bibi Hawa (peace be upon him) was born from the left rib of Adam (peace be upon him). Then, their relationship and marriage started the human race and this caravan will continue till the Day of Judgment. For example, if the sexes of men and women were different from each other, that is, the sexes of women were of the form of jinns or animals, then the man would not be able to get the pleasure from his wife that is due to the fact that the husband and wife are of the same appearance. can be obtained from Otherwise, men and women start hating each other. God Almighty has special mercy on us humans. The meaning of this word of the Holy Qur'an is that when a man loves his married wife the same way, on the other hand, this married wife also loves her husband as much. . And mercy towards husband and wife means that the man provides all the worldly facilities to his wife, because Allah has made it mandatory for the man to fulfill the non-maintenance of the woman after the man and the woman are tied in marriage. has made However, a person gets this peace and comfort only by joining the bond of husband and wife, which is established only by marrying each other according to the laws and decrees of the Muhammadan Shariat. And the couple mentioned in the Holy Quran. It refers to the couple who are getting married. While Islam does not recognize an illegal relationship, neither a husband and wife nor a couple, but such a couple has been called Zani in Qaraab Majeed. The Qur'an prescribes severe punishments for establishing an illicit relationship. In this effort, conscious people related to the current culture are trying to persuade day and night that marriage should be abolished in Islamic countries as well as the immorality spread in the western society and every man and woman should marry each other of their own free will. When they want to commit adultery and commit adultery as a couple (kapil), and then instead of punishing such adulterous men and women, they should be given the rights that an Islamic couple and a legal couple enjoy.⁵

Allah Ta'ala not only ordered to keep the family system together, but also ordered to spend on weak relatives in the family, as stated in this blessed verse.

"يسألونك ماذا ينفقون قل ما انفقتم من خير فلولوالدين والا قريبن والىتامى'
والمساكين وابن السبيل وما تفعلوا من خير فان الله به علىهم"⁶

People ask the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) whether he should spend. Tell them that whatever wealth you spend on your parents, family relatives, orphans, the poor and those on a journey, they all have a right to that wealth and wealth, and whatever good deeds you do, Allah will reward you for it. He knows goodness very well, since man is born weak by nature.

Since Allah Almighty does not want to suppress desires and does not want to leave them open, therefore He ordered marriage between men and women. happens. Allowed up to four wives. Knowing the weakness of human emotions, Allah taught a

pure sexual system. Imam Bukhari said: There is no pressure in religion, it is only regulated. As described in the chapter of Bukhari's Kitab al-Nikah, the blessed hadith is this.

Muhammad sallallaahu 'alayhi wa sallam arrived, then the Prophet sallallaahu 'alaihi wa sallam asked the noble companions that you had said these things. listen ! I swear by Allah! I fear Allah the most out of all of you. And I am the most pious abstainer among you (humans), but if I fast, I also break the fast. I pray (Tahjud prayer) and sleep and I (peace be upon him) also marry women. He who does not act in the way I have told him is not from me. By bringing this hadith, it is intended to explain the importance of marriage for the purpose of the hadith that a man and a woman tie themselves in the bond of marriage is a strictly necessary act in Islam. which will make the family system strong and stable. At the same time, this hadith also sheds light on the reality of Islam, which shows that Islam is the religion of nature against the world religions. Islam wants to build both the world and the religion. Wrongly Turk is not convinced of the world.⁷ A universal last religion had to have these attributes, that's why it was declared as abrogated religion and declared as the last religion of mankind.⁸

Importance of maintaining the structure of the family system

Islamic Shari'ah has defined the principles of maintaining the structure of the family system, we can live a good life only by following them. Because the family system can only survive on paying the rights of the people and feeling others.

Man is the name of both man and woman, and woman shares the path of survival with man. A man alone cannot face all the challenges of knowledge and practice unless he is accompanied by a woman, because women play a very important role in shaping and beautifying the family system in a good way. If there is any disturbance in the family system, then her own family will suffer, and if the family benefits, then her own family will benefit. It helps in keeping. If any evil is found in the family, this woman will oppose and resist it. Just as it welcomes the good, it also protects against the bad. Islam recognizes the right of a woman and in various matters of life, whether they are individual or collective, she is allowed to express her feelings, opinions, thoughts and choices. And it allows the expression of displeasure. This expression is within its limits, language, expression, writing and composition, so that whatever the means, Islam does not impose any restrictions on it, but encourages it, so it is said in Surah Towba of the Holy Qur'an: ⁹ "(Translation) Muslim men and Muslim women are equal companions, they enjoin doing good and forbidding doing wrong." That's why Muhammad and his Companions, may God bless him and grant him peace, did everything from household affairs to state affairs. He took advice from women and followed them. Hazrat Hasan Basri, may God bless him and grant him peace, mentions one of the good things about the Prophet, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, saying: "The Prophet, peace be upon him, used to consult with

women, and she used to give an opinion that he, may God bless him and grant him peace, would adopt."¹⁰

Inquiries on not maintaining the structure of the family system on the day of Mohshar

Those who turn their backs on each other because of the family system and worldly comforts will have to give an account on the Day of Judgment, as the Holy Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: Each one of you is a ruler and from each one (this There will be a question about the subjects of So the Imam is the ruler, there will be a question about him. A man is the ruler of his wife and children and there will be a question about him. A woman is the ruler of her husband's wealth and there will be a question about it. A slave is the ruler of his master's wealth and he will be questioned. Yes, each one of you is a ruler and everyone will be questioned. On the Day of Judgment, everyone will be questioned about his subjects, so it is important for a man to take care of his family and prevent them from doing bad things, otherwise they will also be with such bad people in Hell on the Day of Judgment. Why didn't you stop your family members from doing bad deeds? ¹¹ It was said in the holy verse,

"قوالنفسكم واهليكم ناراً" ^{١٢}

With love and gentleness, the system of home and children is better. The Holy Prophet (PBUH) used to treat his wives very politely, sometimes he used to joke with his wives, sometimes he used to compete with his wives and he used to forgive their wives' tongues. We should learn lessons from the Prophet's life so that we too can become the best rulers of our home and family system. Then, in the same way, people who do not act and encourage to save the family system in the Holy Quran will deserve punishment on the Day of Muhshar, as it is mentioned in Surah Tahirim of the Holy Quran that (translation) O Muslims, bring yourselves and your family members to hell. Protect from the fire of (because the fuel of Hell will be people and stones). Continue to reform and organize religious education and training for them so that all these people can avoid becoming the fuel of hell.¹³ In the Holy Qur'an, he said

"فَهَلْ عَسَيْتُمْ إِن تَوَلَّيْتُمْ أَن تُفْسِدُوا فِي الْأَرْضِ وَتَقَطَّعُوا أَرْحَامَكُمْ أُولَئِكَ الَّذِينَ لَعَنَهُمُ اللَّهُ فَأَصَمَّهُمْ وَأَعَمَّى أَبْصَارَهُمْ" ^{١٤}

"Now, can anything else be expected from you people except that if you turn away, you will create mischief in the land and cut the ties of kinship? These are the people whom Allah has cursed and made them blind and deaf."

In support of these teachings and commandments of the Holy Qur'an, the hadiths of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) have also been

included: It is narrated from Hazrat Abd al-Rahman bin Awf (may Allah be pleased with him) that:

"قَالَ سَمِعْتُ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يَقُولُ قَالَ اللَّهُ أَنَا الرَّحْمَنُ وَهِيَ الرَّحْمُ شَقَقْتُ
لَهَا اسْمًا مِنْ اسْمِي مَنْ وَصَلَهَا وَصَلْتَهُ وَمَنْ قَطَعَهَا بَتَّه" ١٥

Muhammad (peace be upon him) said: "The Lord Almighty says, I am Merciful, and this kinship, which is called Rahm, is a word that Allah has taken out from His name, so whoever keeps close contact with his dear relatives and relatives. And if their charioteer behaves ethically, then the Lord Almighty says that I am connected with him and whoever breaks the family relationship, I also break the relationship with him."

Although the basis of family in Islam consists of husband and wife. And the parents, sons, daughters, grandchildren, brothers and sisters, uncles and aunts, uncles and aunts connected with them are also considered as seeds of praise in connecting the family system. In Islam, the family system is not contracted, but rather expanded and extended. Which consists of children of uncles and aunts (Asabat) and children of maternal uncles and aunts (Arham).

Islam says that the family system can only be strengthened by the marriage of a man and a woman, in the words of the blessed Hadith:

"لَمْ يَرْلَمْتَحَابِينَ مِثْلَ النِّكَاحِ" ١٦

There is no such thing as intermarriage for those who are at odds with each other. Should be given. If the affection of a boy and a girl starts to grow towards each other, instead of establishing an illicit relationship, both the boy and the girl should establish a legitimate marriage relationship. Because it is better than having an illicit relationship, however, there are other conditions of marriage. That is, the permission of the guardian of the woman, the right of dowry, consent and acceptance and the presence of two witnesses must be found.

Similarly, marriage has been encouraged in many places in Quran and Hadith. Our beloved Prophet Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa (peace be upon him) said: If a man

(Regarding wealth) If he is rich, he should get married, because by marrying, his eyes and private parts are protected from evil deeds like immorality, and if a Muslim cannot afford to marry, then he wants such a Muslim to fast after childbirth. He should keep it, because fasting will not cause evil eye, inshallah.¹⁷

The 21st Century and the Western Family

One of the beauty and blessings of Islam is its family system. Among all the religions and civilizations found on the earth today, Islam is the only religion which insists Muslims to maintain a family system. The family system has spread in Europe, America and Western countries. In these societies, the freedom to have illicit relations before marriage has turned them into beasts. Homosexuality is spreading like a terrible epidemic in our family system, due to which legal and constitutional forms are being given in some countries to enforce the family system. Otherwise, the rate of giving or getting divorce has been gradually increasing within just two years of the formal marriage of husband and wife. According to the survey, there is a large number of newborns who do not have any means of knowing their birth and parentage. As a result of this situation, some people have to resort to their mother's name on their passport or other legal documents.

There can be no doubt that the religion of Islam gave women not only a place in running the family system but also gave them the right to inherit. For example: right to education, right to employment, right to marry of choice, right to live a free and independent life, right to vote and contest elections. But if we consider the present modern civilization, women are oppressed as much as they were oppressed before. According to an American Time magazine survey of March 20, 1972: "Despite the tireless efforts of the United States, the number of women who choose to live in America is still about the same as it was twenty years ago. Men in America are still practically It's sexist." Women still have only a traditional status vis-à-vis men in America. They are only enthusiastically taken up in fields that depend on women, such as fashion or acting, as Claire Lewis said: Power, Rs. And sex are the three greatest values in America today. And women have no access to power, except through their husbands. They get money, more through sex, legitimate or illegitimate.¹⁸ A woman, Helen McLean, said:

"Fewer women have been placed in administrative positions on Earth than the number of men America has sent to the moon.¹⁹ In the modern Western world, it is still considered frivolous for a woman to be given a high government position. In a 1972 poll, a majority of American voters said they would prefer a black male president to a female president."²⁰

In the 2009 elections, the Americans practically proved that a black man, Barack Hussein Obama, was elected as president, but no white woman was elected, Even a woman could not become president.²¹ A Russian scientist, Anton Namlov, presenting his experiences and observations, writes: Nowhere in the whole world has the struggle to give equal rights to men and women been seen as much as in the Soviet Union and Russia.²²

The people in the West have a wrong concept of living a life system and living with freedom, the result of which is that the relationship between a man and a woman started

to be established only after marriage, even a pure relationship like Nikah. As a result, the independent life that was created due to this has not only created a number of family system distortions, but has also created social problems. According to the research of 1993, rape cases are happening in America every day according to the average of 1900.²³

The reason for which is that the western family system is completely destroyed due to the woman leaving the house, which the people of the West are also worried about today. are more advanced than those who are employed as office clerks, store managers, salesmen, employed in educational services in schools, post houses, wire houses, French banks and Credit Lyonnais banks. It is 100% correct that the job has taken these women far away from their homes, due to which the beauty of the homes is getting ruined. After giving data on the business and academic progress of American women,²⁴ Madam du Afreneau writes: But from these things, it is clear that the woman keeps herself busy outside the home for the sake of learning knowledge and skills. Khati, then the man is forced to divorce his wife because of not giving time to the husband. As today many cases of divorce can be seen in the West. ²⁵ Because in the West, the sacred relationship of marriage and the stage from the birth of a new-born child to its care is considered a burden, the family system has reached the brink of destruction and therefore the family system has become distorted. Because of this, the elderly parents in the house were not in a happy situation, then the western government forced them to keep them there by creating institutions called Old Home. There is no place in the western culture for the "adult girl" in the western civilization. There is no place in the western culture for the "aged woman". is, because this youthful beauty of a woman, this attractive feminine attraction ends when she gets old, which is a physical process. Because of this, a woman living in the West loses her position after she gets old. If he does not accept it, he does not even get a share in the rights" This is Western in its worst form Sadiq has come in favor of the woman, and you and your close children do not care about the old mother.²⁶

The truth of this can be estimated from the incident that: A woman in America went to the court that my son cares more about his dog than me, the court should order him to have at least the dog as much as I care about him. Do it! The court there ruled that the dog was raised by him, so it is obligatory on him to serve the dog and take care of it, but it is not obligatory on him to take care of you.²⁷ In the words of Farid Wajdi:

"Today the poor woman of the West is no more important than a toy in the hands of a man."²⁸

In the words of Dr. Zakir Naik:

"The people of the West have practically reduced women to the level of prostitutes, made women an object that men enjoy, art and culture. Behind the beautiful curtains, her dignity is used for a few

ticks, so that she is left as a toy in the hands of sex-seekers and entrepreneurs, without the woman herself realizing what she is doing."²⁹

In other words, in the modern family system, a woman who earns a lot of money and also has beauty is seen with respect. You also shine, who cover their chastity and chador and trample the sanctity of the house wall and become a film actor and a heroine in a drama and do all this for the sake of a few bucks, while in the society women are not treated well. This kind of woman is not seen by sight and is not respected in any society. Because it is clear that in the West, when a woman is old, when she is no longer able to earn, she loses her good voice, when she is in need of the service of her children, then she is sent to the old home. Baqi is forced to live in the same old home and spend the last days of her life where she amuses herself by raising dogs and cats. In view of all these, in the next line, we shed light on the serious consequences of the deterioration of the family system.

1. The number of illicit relationships between men and women increased and a new term partner was invented.
2. Marriages started failing and the divorce rate started increasing.
3. There was a psychological impact on children, there was an increase in emotionally disturbed children.
4. A new group of single mothers came into existence who take care of children born as a result of sexual relations.
5. The modern society is facing the problem of teenage pregnancy. Because of this freedom, teenage girls get pregnant due to sexual experiences. According to research, 10-year-old girls in Britain gave birth to children.
6. As a result of the violation of moral values, there has been an increase in sexually deviant people. Now homosexuality is an acceptable behavior in the West, and now the Protestant Church has accepted homosexuals as priests. Western states have taken over many of the duties of the family, so the need for a close family is no longer there.³⁰

Summary

The most important institution in social institutions is the family. This institution provides individuals to the society, the better the environment of this institution, the more good people will be available to the society. It becomes difficult to find good people. And the important role in running the family system is that of a woman, whether she is a widow or a sister. In any case, the importance of all these in maintaining the family system cannot be denied. If the woman in the house is respected, then this family will also have dignity and their consideration in fulfilling the rights of the women in the family. If done, there will be peace in this family. Contrary to all this, where there is restlessness and dissatisfaction in the family system, there will be no good people available to the society.

The study of human history shows that the honor and dignity of the daughter of Eve remained in the human society as long as the teachings of the prophets (peace be upon them) were followed, but since the teachings of the prophets (peace be upon them) were forgotten, or The situation of the family system is also present in front of you since that time, or it was mixed with it. As a result, the society could not have better people, but the social system was subject to destruction and chaos.

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